

D6.3: Workshop Programme satellite to the Annual Scientific Meeting

Year 2 (2019)

Responsible Partner: SVA, Sweden

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
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DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Work Package 6 Task #	Task 6.2: Workshop Programme satellite to the Annual Scientific Meeting
Lead Organising Institute	National Veterinary Institute, Sweden
Lead Workshop Organiser (LWO)	Professor Ann Lindberg
Organising Committee	Professor Ann Lindberg, Dr Valerie de Waele, Prof Roberto La Ragione, Dr Piyali Basu, Dr Jade Passey
Collaborating Organising Institutes	University of Surrey (UoS) Sciensano (Belgium)
Due month of the report	24
Actual submission month	24
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.</i> <i>OTHER</i>	R
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU

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Introduction

Annual Scientific Meetings (ASMs) are held within a One Health concept specifically showcasing the knowledge and scientific advances in Joint Research Projects and Joint Integrative activities.

Each ASM has a satellite workshop, organised through this task, focusing on one of the priority areas for the One Health European Joint Programme (OHEJP). These meetings provide opportunities for early-career researchers and researchers who work in an area related to the theme to present a short talk and provide a platform to share and discuss unpublished work. Invited speakers present longer talks on expert topics related to the theme of the workshop. Each workshop also includes an accompanying e-learning package for participants.

The workshops provide opportunities for collaboration and knowledge and skills exchange between OHEJP partners. These scientific and social interactions are an important goal and aspect of integration of the workshop. Wherever possible, the workshop will contribute to building a future consortium to support the sustainability of the OHEJP (WP7), and to extend the OHEJP outside the EU in alignment with the “Go Global” approach.

The OHEJP ASM Satellite Workshop 2019 was organised by the National Veterinary Institute, Sweden in collaboration with Sciensano, Belgium and University of Surrey, UK. The half-day workshop was hosted at the Teagasc Conference Centre, Dublin, Ireland on 21st May 2019 where the ASM was held.

Theme

The theme for the workshop was Data Management and Digital Innovation.

Aims and Objectives

The workshop aimed to provide a platform to discuss digital innovation within and outside the OHEJP consortium, in addition to developing an understanding and interest in data management plans. This proved to be an excellent opportunity to understand how data management plans can be applied to one’s research.

Satellite Workshop speakers

A photograph and short biography can be found [here](#) on our website for each speaker. This page was updated regularly as each speaker was confirmed as part of the promotional strategy to increase awareness of the event.

Logistical arrangements

The workshop hosted 44 delegates who all belonged to the One Health EJP Consortium. This half-day workshop was free to register to attend, and lunch and coffee breaks were provided by the conference venue.

A registration process was designed and implemented through the OHEJP website. During the registration process, the relevant personal data was collected for example institute, One Health domain and OHEJP research domain that represents their work, role within their institute and

involvement with the OHEJP. Additionally, any dietary requirements, and permission to publish photographs taken and testimonials.

Promotional Campaign

The Promotional Campaign was managed by the OHEJP Communications Team.

A '[Save the Date](#)' promotional flyer was created and validated with the satellite workshop organizing team once the dates and venues had been confirmed. This was promoted and distributed through the following OHEJP channels: the OHEJP website, OHEJP Twitter and LinkedIn social media channels, and email communications.

Once the details of the first version of the satellite workshop programme had been confirmed and the registration process had been put in place, a detailed double-sided [flyer](#) was created and validated with the satellite workshop organizing team. This was also promoted and distributed through the OHEJP channels mentioned above.

Programme

Please refer to the [programme](#) on the [flyer](#). The programme consisted of an introductory lecture by Niamh Brennan, Trinity College Dublin, who is Ireland's representative to OpenAire. She presented the initiative, and explained how it links to EOSC, the European Open Science Cloud and how these new resources could be of benefit to the One Health EJP partners. The 30-minute introductory lecture was followed by a practical workshop (the e-learning component) on how to plan your data management. This part was facilitated by Georgina Cherry from the University of Surrey (UoS), and Mickele Francisco, a data management expert engaged by Sciensano to support the development of the overarching OHEJP data management plan, and the guidance to Joint Research Projects (JRPs) and Joint Integrative Projects (JIPs). Comprehensive material had been developed for the workshop and was used by the participants to outline the major considerations needed in their data management planning.

The second part of the satellite workshop was dedicated to presentations related to digital innovation; first a talk on the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) within the scope of the OHEJP - for tackling foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats. The concluding talk was related to the use of machine learning - another AI-based technology - in digital pathology to improve cancer diagnosis. Both talks on digital innovation were given by speakers from UoS - Nikos Papachristou and Ambra Morisi and addressed aspects of human and animal health care that are likely to become heavily influenced by the currently ongoing digital transformation in society.

Delegates

The workshop hosted 44 delegates who all belonged to the One Health EJP Consortium. The three health domains that constitute the One Health concept were represented at this workshop, demonstrating a truly One Health Approach. Furthermore, the three key OHEJP research domains were also well represented at this workshop.

The majority of the attendees to this workshop were researchers and PIs at academic institutes within the OHEJP consortium, however there was also representation from PhD students, including OHEJP PhD students and industry. It was exciting to see the interest from PhD students as encouraging the use of data management plans early on in their scientific career is of increasing importance in research.

Certificates of Attendance

The Communications Team provided electronic copies of the Certificates of Attendance to all delegates who registered. The template can be found in [Annex 3](#).

Testimonials

Permission to publish these testimonials must be sought. This is usually done during the registration application process.

Lead Organiser Testimonial

Professor Ann Lindberg: "We were very happy to see such large interest in this workshop, which covered a very hot and new topic for both young and more senior researchers. It constituted an important milestone for the OHEJP community in its collaborative learning about structured data management, and on how to push towards making research data more open - a key requirement from funders, now and in the future."

Examples of other testimonials collected

Georgina Cherry (Lecturer): "The workshop was well-organised and made the process of writing a data management plan much clearer to me. The handout from the workshop was comprehensive and I will refer back to it in future."

Ambre Morisi (Early Career Researcher Presenter and delegate): "This is a great conference that attracts people with different expertise. The presentations were extremely interesting and of great quality. I have learned a lot from this conference and it's definitely a good place to initiate collaboration and to brainstorm new ideas."

Delegate: "The 2019 preconference satellite workshop of the EJP One Health ASM focused largely on data managements plans. This was a particularly useful subject as many funders now require submission of a data management plan alongside proposals. In particular it was very useful to have time during the workshop to not only see examples of data management plan templates, but also have time allocated to begin completing a plan and discuss with experts and other delegates best practice. I am an early career researcher who will shortly begin applying for my own funding and so this workshop allowed me to critically think not only about the data I might generate but how to manage it in a way which is accessible for funders, publishers and other researchers."

Photos

Written permission must have been taken from all those in any photographs taken. This is usually done during the registration application process.

Image 1: Niamh Brenan, assistant librarian from Trinity College Dublin gave an introduction to OpenAire and the European Open Science cloud.

Image 2: Georgina Cherry, from the University of Surrey's vHive presented Data Management Plans and their importance in collaborative projects.

Image 3: Mickle Francisco, from Sciensano, led the practical session where attendees were tasked with considering their research and a suitable data management plan for their data. All workshop speakers were available to help the attendees with ideas and advice.

Image 4: Nikos Papachristou, an expert in machine learning from the University of Surrey, presented how AI and machine learning can be successfully applied to the One Health concept.

Image 5: PhD students, Ambra Morisi and Taran Rai from the University of Surrey, present their research on AI and digital pathology.

Internal Events Survey information

The European Commission requires all dissemination and communication activities, and events to be reported. **Please complete both the [Internal Events Survey](#) and the table below as accurately as possible.**

The Internal Events Survey has been completed.

Name of the activity:	One Health EJP Satellite Workshop 2019		
Date:	21st May 2019		
Place:	Teagasc Conference Centre, Ashtown, Dublin, Ireland		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop	Y	Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer	Y	Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media	Y	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website	Y	Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	41	Media	0
Industry	3	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		

Annex 1: “Save the Date” Promotional Flyer

Save the Date!

One Health EJP ASM Satellite Workshop 2019: Digital Innovation and Data Management

Date: 21st May 2019

Time: 12.00-17.30

Location: Teagasc Conference Centre,
Dublin, Ireland

More details to be announced!

 <https://onehealthejp.eu/asm-satellite-workshop>

Find us on social media:

 One Health EJP

#OneHealthEJP #OHEJPASM2019

Annex 2: Satellite Workshop Promotional Flyer

One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting Satellite Workshop 2019; Digital Innovation and Data Management

What is the ASM Satellite Workshop?
This year's workshop will focus on Digital Innovation and Data Management in One Health.

Who is the workshop for?
The workshop is targeted to PhD students, all researchers, project leaders and institute data managers.

What is the aim of this workshop?
The workshop aims to provide a platform to discuss digital innovation within the One Health EJP consortium. In addition to developing an understanding and interest in data management plans. This is an excellent opportunity to understand how data management plans can be applied to your research.

Date: Tuesday 21st May	Time: 12.00-17.30pm	Location: Teagasc Conference Centre
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For more information and to register for this event please visit
<https://onehealthejp.eu/asm-satellite-workshop>

Keep up to date on our website and social media pages!

 @OneHealthEJP One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting
 company/h2020-one-health-ejp 22nd-24th May 2019, Dublin, Ireland
www.ohejp.com

#OneHealthEJP #OHEJPASM2019

AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY

Satellite workshop on Data Management and Digital Innovation Programme

Time	Session	Speaker
<i>Lunch- 12:00 – 13:00</i>		
13:00 – 13:10	Welcome, introduction	Ann Lindberg, WP4 and Roberto La Ragione, WP6
13:10 – 13:40	Introduction on OpenAIRE and European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) in health research	Niamh Brennan, Trinity College Library, Dublin
<i>13:40 – 13:45- Short break</i>		
13:45 – 15:00	Workshop: Planning your Data Management, part 1	Facilitators: Georgina Cherry, University of Surrey and Miekele Francisco, Sciensano
<i>15:00 – 15:30- Coffee break</i>		
15:30 – 16:45	Workshop: Planning your Data Management, part 2	Facilitators: Georgina Cherry, University of Surrey and Miekele Francisco, Sciensano
16:45 – 17:10	The value of Artificial Intelligence in tackling Foodborne Zoonoses (FBZ), Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR) and Emerging Threats (ET)	Nikos Papachristou, University of Surrey
17:10 – 17:25	Machine learning in digital pathology to improve cancer diagnosis in humans and animals	Ambra Morisi, University of Surrey
<i>17:30- Close</i>		

Conference Organisers:
Ann Lindberg- Work Package 4 Leader
Roberto La Ragione- Work Package 6 Leader
Valerie De Waele- Sciensano

NATIONAL VETERINARY INSTITUTE

Annex 3: Certificate of Attendance template

CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PRESENTED TO:

Recipient Name

For participating in the One Health EJP Digital Innovation and Data Management Workshop
held on 21st May 2019 at Teagasc Conference Centre, Dublin, Ireland.

The workshop covered the context of Research Data Management (RDM) in terms of policies, rationale, requirements, infrastructure and supports.
The FAIR principles, metadata and practical usage of DMP online was presented and practiced.

PRESENTED BY:

Ann Lindberg
Work Package 4 Leader

and

Roberto La Ragione
Work Package 6 Leader

This workshop is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP. This programme has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.